
Nigerian Employees' Attitude towards Foreign Products and its Dynamics with Consumer Ethnocentrism and Locus of Control: A Descriptive Analysis

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Abstract:

To the knowledge of the researcher of work at hand, no study has researched on the dynamics of both Ethnocentrism and Locus of Control on Willingness to Buy Foreign Product, which forms the basic purpose of this paper. The descriptive research primarily based in Nigeria employed non-probability convenience sampling and sample size of 238 covered mutually private and public sector employees. Cronbach's Alpha, Pearson correlation, One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), regression analysis, One Sample T-Test, Pearson Chi-Square, mean, standard deviation and Percentages as statistical measures was used to analyse and reach the research objectives. Though actual purchase behaviour for overseas products was not in purview of this study, it was found that in Northern Nigeria moderate levels of ethnocentrism was recorded for the employees surveyed. Nevertheless, only internal LOC was correlated with ethnocentrism. In the end, the paper provides various business and managerial recommendations and repercussions for researchers and management practitioners alike vis-à-vis afore mentioned variables.

Keywords: Ethnocentrism, Willingness to Buy Foreign Product, Locus of Control, Employees, Nigeria

1. Introduction

In the cotemporary globalised world, marketing of products and services are not limited to their country of origin, rather businesses have to operate in other markets too. This can be an issue for organisations if potential consumers in the country where they want to operate are not receptive of their products due to high ethnocentric tendencies there. According to Shimp and Sharma (1987), ethnocentrism is a phenomenon where ethnocentric individuals despite of having lower quality domestic product (considering their country to be superior) prefer to buy them as against foreign ones. Additionally, ethnocentric consumers deem purchasing products from other countries to be immoral, and perceive that it also leads to damaging local economy and creating unemployment (Xin and Seo, 2019). Ethnocentric tendencies of people are formed in the childhood and social factors can hardly change these predispositions (Hooghe, Reeskens and Stolle, 2007), hence the importance of the present study to understand this very significant construct.

Additionally, purchase intention which stimulates a consumer to make purchasing decision according to Rahman, Haque and Khan (2012) means the readiness and willingness to purchase any specific product or for that matter service. This consumer decision making process according to the authors incorporates “willingness to consider buying”, “buying intention in the future” and “decision of repurchase”. According to Carter (2009) purchase intention of a consumer also known as ‘willingness to buy’ or ‘reluctance to buy’ constitutes their subjective intentions about prospective purchases. It is well established that if a consumer has dislike for a particular country, his Willingness to Buy Foreign Product (WBFP) from that country would be negatively affected. The consequences of whether the product in question is good or bad have no bearing on his willingness to purchase foreign product if animosity with that country is perceived by a consumer (Klein, Ettenson and Morris, 1998; Quang, Dinh Chien and Long, 2017).

The next pertinent variable used in the present research is Locus of Control (LOC) which refers to the degree of an individual’s perception of their control over their lives, and environment. If a person believes that the control of his life is in his hands, he is deemed to have internal locus and if his belief is that whatever happens in his life is due to uncertainties, fate, luck or chance or other environmental factors, he has external LOC (Rotter, 1954; Lefcourt, 1976).

2. Literature Review

A number of studies have investigated the concept of consumer ethnocentrism and its effect on inclination towards foreign products, one such being on food products done with 2250 Nigerian consumers by Kilders, Caputo and Liverpool-Tasie (2021). The research indicated that higher consumer ethnocentrism leads to lesser preference for foreign products. The next contemplative issue is to know the factors effecting consumer ethnocentrism, where education, income and social class as demographic variables have been designated to contribute to a person’s level of consumer ethnocentrism (Sousa, Nobre and Farhangmehr, 2018). Literature from young Indonesian consumers numbering 175 as sample size suggest that they perceive local products to be inferior quality wise (Purwanto, 2016). The study further suggested that perception about the quality of overseas merchandise has a positive and substantial bearing on foreign purchase intentions.

The next step for a consumer is to make purchasing intention, whether it is positive or negative, it is guided by the ethnocentrism levels of the consumers (Baughn and Yaprak, 1993; Nijssen and Douglas, 2004). Even more than marketing strategies, ethnocentrism hold

bigger sway when it comes to making buying decisions (Herche, 1994). A research done in New Zealand by Watson and Wright (2000) came with the finding that consumers who are ethnocentric in their outlook are inclined towards purchasing merchandises from those countries which are similar in culture, if some product is not accessible locally for them. However extant literature also points to the fact that country of origin is not always the influence for purchase decision, case in point is the Chinese study by Wong, Polonsky and Garma (2008) where the reason given for such behaviour is economic globalisation which makes the consumers to consider the world as one country.

Another Chinese study done by Klein, Ettenson and Morris (1998), also indicates that product quality or judgment is of no value for consumers if they hold an adverse attitude for a particular country, which may lead to their purchase behaviour of not buying any product or services from that country. An Israeli study point out that purchase of local products and services are positively influenced greatly by consumer ethnocentrism. More ethnocentric buyers will look for domestic goods rather than going for those which have origins in some other countries (Shoham and Brencic, 2003). Therefore, it can be safely said that actual purchase behaviour is definitely effected by willingness to purchase (Phau, Sequeira and Dix, 2009) and ethnocentrism plays a very dominant role in it. It is further supported through results of a cross cultural research of USA and Russia, where Durvasula (1997) has put that inclination towards domestic products and its purchase is highly influenced by greater propensity of consumer ethnocentrism.

Literature additionally suggests that there does exist a relationship between willingness to purchase foreign products and actual purchase, that these two are interrelated (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980; Liao and Hsieh, 2013). Further researches put forward that consumer ethnocentrism also has a substantial effect on consumers' willingness to acquire products from foreign countries (Wang and Chen, 2004). Ethnocentrism is a very critical variable for marketing professionals, particularly those engaged in international marketing. These professionals would like to market their products according to preference of the consumers, which is thereby effected by their ethnocentric levels which again influences their WBFP (Balabanis and Diamantopoulos, 2004; Altintas and Tokol, 2007).

Solely if we examine the African context, apart from those done to study the perception of the Mozambican consumers for South African products or Zimbabwean consumers for poultry from South Africa, researches pertaining to consumer animosity for foreign products are rather limited (John and Brady, 2011a; John and Brady, 2011b; Makanyeza and du Toit, 2016). However, several African studies, case in point those done in Nigeria (where the study at hand is based), Ghana or for that matter Tanzania, consumers aspire for foreign made products as against local brands mainly due to narrow product choices they have owing limited manufacturing capabilities (Festervand and Sokoya, 1994; Okechuku and Onyemah, 1999; Lysonski and Durvasula, 2013; Kisawike, 2015; Kiriri, 2018).

Though existing literature is devoid of much studies related to LOC and ethnocentric buying behaviour or for that matter WBFP, there is no denying the fact that LOC does influence the choice a consumer makes in purchasing a product, which includes external searches made before buying decision (Howard and Sheth, 1969). Internal LOC has been found to be associated positively with willingness to buy locally produced food stuffs in a study by Hempel and Roosen (2021), where more internal the LOC was, there was more preference for such items. The present study also consequently aims to add to the limited body of research

concerned with the understanding of the interplay between LOC and ethnocentric tendencies along with WBFP among the employees in African context.

3. Theoretical Background

The theoretical underpinning of consumer ethnocentrism is Social Identity Theory given by Henri Tajfel and John Turner in the decades 1970 and 1980. Established on intergroup behaviour, the theory describes the phenomenon of the 'ingroup' and 'outgroup', which in turn explains the concept of ethnocentrism and the consumer purchase behaviour based on it. The psychological concept of consumer ethnocentrism postulates that the consumers deem it to be improper and perhaps immoral to buy products or services from other countries, considered the outgroup. The ethnocentric individuals perceive their group to be superior than others, thereby rejecting them and accepting only those which are similar to them (Tajfel and Turner, 1979; Tajfel and Turner, 1986; Shimp and Sharma, 1987; Netemeyer, Durvasula and Lichtenstein, 1991; Turner, 1999; Benwell and Stokoe, 2006; Turner and Reynolds, 2010).

To explain the purchase intention/behaviour or for that matter WBFP of a consumer, theory of planned behaviour (TPB) developed by Ajzen (1991) explained here would be useful. The basic premise of the theory is that an individual executes a particular behaviour if he intends to perform it and these behavioural intentions are formed on the basis of attitude towards the behaviour, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control.

The origins of the concept of LOC can be traced to Social Learning Theory of personality given by Julian B. Rotter in 1954. It developed into the definition given by Herbert M. Lefcourt in the year 1976 as "...a generalized expectancy for internal as opposed to external control of reinforcements" (Lefcourt, 1976). According to Rotter (1966), there are some external forces beyond a person's control and LOC is the extent to which people perceive they can regulate them. Those who can control various events in their lives are designated as having internal LOC as opposed to those who believe that luck or chance influence their lives along with the outside factors are theorised as having external LOC.

4. Research Problem, Gap and Significance of Study

Research problem encounters a principal gap of not having adequate empirical investigation of the effect of LOC on consumer ethnocentrism as well as WBFP which the present study tries to fill, especially in African context. There are many studies which have delved into the interplay of consumer ethnocentrism and WBFP, but putting them in African or Nigerian context indicates one of the importance of the present study, for both private as well as public sector organisations. The understanding of the three principle variables as already discussed above is of utmost importance for not only corporate buyers but individual ones too vis-à-vis purchase decisions made.

5. Research Objectives

The primary aim of the present research is to investigate the interplay among the variables consumer ethnocentrism, WBFP and LOC in Nigeria. The study further intended to determine the relationship of these dependent variables on independent demographic variables, keeping the Nigerian employees as consumers drawn from various government and private sector organisations as the contextual background. The study also aims to present managerial implications and suggestions for marketing/management professionals and companies who are working in international operations to deal with the influences of consumer ethnocentrism on their businesses.

6. Conceptual Framework and Statement of Hypotheses

Figure 1: Research Model

The research model initially proposes consumer ethnocentrism, LOC and sociodemographic variables as independent variables to find their effect on the dependent variable willingness to buy foreign product. Additionally, the interaction of LOC acting as constant on consumer ethnocentrism (here taken as dependent variable) and that of demographic variables (as constant) on LOC (acting as dependent variable) was also anticipated to be researched. Therefore, following hypotheses were tested in the course of this research:

- H₁ There will be significant negative correlation between employee consumer ethnocentrism and WBFP.
- H₂ There will be a significant relationship between employee LOC and ethnocentrism.
- H₃ There will be a significant correlation between employee LOC and WBFP.
- H₄ There will be a significant influence of employee LOC on WBFP.
- H₅ There will be a significant variation for consumer ethnocentrism based on gender, age, education and work experience of Nigerian employees.
- H₆ Consumer WBFP will be significantly influenced by gender, marital status, age, education and work experience for Nigerian employees.
- H₇ There will be a significant difference for marital status, gender, age, education and work experience of Nigerian employees vis-à-vis LOC.

7. Methodology

7.1. Instrumentation Scales and Reliability Statistics

Since the present study has descriptive research design, the first scale used in the research to measure consumer ethnocentrism was the six item short version Consumer Ethnocentrism Tendency Scale (CETSCALE) adopted from Shimp and Sharma (1987) and modified to Nigerian context. To measure the purchase intension of respondents for foreign products, another adopted and modified six item scale was used called Willingness to Buy Foreign Products Scale, WBFPS (Klien, Ettenson and Morris, 1998). Both the scales are Likert-type in nature where the responses were rated from 1 being very strongly disagree to 7 being very strongly agree. Additionally, higher mean score meant greater degree of ethnocentrism for the CETSCALE, similarly it also amounted to more positive attitude towards buying a product from foreign country for WBFPS. Lastly to measure the construct of LOC, a Sapp and Harrod (1993) constructed nine item brief form of Levenson's LOC Scale (LCS) was employed.

Items added up giving higher scores reflected greater internal LOC. Unlike the above two scales, this was a five point Likert-type scale from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree. Cronbach's Alpha value of .802 for CETSCALE, .807 for WBFPS and .701 for LCS showed high level of internal consistency according to the standards set by Nunnally and Bernstein (1994).

7.2. Research Design, Sampling and Statistical Procedures

The present research employed survey method design and the data was gathered through a Google form link, following the non-probability convenience sampling criteria. Statistical Tools included for analysis purpose were Cronbach's Alpha, Pearson correlation, One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), regression analysis, One Sample T-Test, Pearson Chi-Square, mean, standard deviation and Percentages. All the analysis of raw data was done using SPSS version 23.

7.3. Demographic Statistics

The results of the study showed that out of total 238 respondents included, majority were in the age group of 20-30 years (43.3%) followed by those in 30-40 year bracket (30.3%). Male respondents were 81.5% and females were 18.5% where majority of 53.4% were married and 46.6% were singles. Having attained high levels of education most of the respondents at 50% got more than 15 years of formal education followed by 10-15 years of education (26.1%). Additionally, 50.8% were having private jobs (73.6% males and 26.4% females) while 49.2% were public sector employees (89.7% males and 10.3% females) and they had mean work experience of 8.67 years.

8. Results and Discussion

8.1 Correlation between Ethnocentrism and WBFP

The range of ethnocentric tendencies according to the scale administered may vary from 6 to 42 points, 6 to 21 being low ethnocentrism, 22-29 medium and 30-42 points being high ethnocentrism. Overall, with 28.36 points, the Nigerian employees as consumers have medium level of ethnocentrism. Pearson correlation employed established a negative relationship between the variables Ethnocentrism and WBFP for Nigerian consumers ($r = -0.255$, $n = 238$, the value of $p = <0.000$) implying more ethnocentric consumers are not willing to buy foreign products, it accepts H_1 . Additionally, strong negative correlations were also found for government employees ($r = -0.315$, $n = 117$, the value of $p = <0.001$) and private workers ($r = -0.190$, $n = 121$, the value of $p = <0.037$) for these two variables taken up separately.

8.2 Effect of LOC on Ethnocentrism

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) analysis carried out to determine the effect of LOC on Ethnocentrism established that with $F(1,236) = .725$, and significance .153 ($p > .05$), there was no significant interaction between the variables LOC and Ethnocentrism for the combined data. Also separately taken government employees $\{F(1,115) = .323$, and significance .571 ($p > .05$)} and private sector employees $\{F(1,119) = .553$, and significance .459 ($p > .05$)} concluded no significant relationship between LOC and Ethnocentrism. It implies that for Nigerian employees whether they have internal LOC or for that matter external LOC it did not affect their ethnocentric tendencies, thereby rejecting H_2 .

8.3 Relationship between LOC and WBFP

However, a very significant correlation was found for LOC and WBFP with $r = 0.391$, $n = 238$, the value of $p = <0.000$. This relationship was also true for government employees ($r =$

0.468, $n = 117$, the value of $p = <0.000$) and private employees ($r = 0.279$, $n = 121$, the value of $p = <0.002$). This establishes that those employees as consumers if they had higher levels of internal LOC were more positive towards the purchase of foreign products, it supports H_3 .

8.4 Regression Analysis to Determine the Effect of LOC on WBFP

Apart from the relationship, influence of LOC (treated here as predictor or constant variable) among the employees on their WBFP (dependent variable) was additionally explored through regression analysis. With the P-Value = .000 (less than .05) it was found that there did exist the effect of LOC on WBFP with 95% confidence interval, 15.3% of the variation in WBFP was due to LOC (since the value of R Square was equal to .153), it confirms H_4 . Additional analysis was conducted to determine the direction of effect of LOC on WBFP. The coefficient regression for LOC was .641 and significance value was .000 ($p < .05$), consequently it means that LOC had a positive influence on WBFP of the employees. It implies that if the LOC of the employees was internal, it was favourable in terms of WBFP for the employees surveyed.

8.5. Relationship between measured constructs and Sociodemographic Characteristics of Respondents

8.5.1. Ethnocentric Tendencies, WBFP and LOC on the basis of Organisation type, Gender, and Marital Status

Ethnocentrism score for government male employees 28.49, government female 27.76, private male workers 29.16 and private female ones being 29.31 points, shows moderate levels. Further, married respondents were more ethnocentric with mean 4.83, standard deviation (sd) 1.283 than singles (mean 4.77, sd 1.241), however there was no statistical backing for the same. Pearson Chi-Square value of 15.212, degree of freedom (df) 4 and asymptotic significance .004 ($<.05$) also evidenced significant difference in marital status and LOC, where married respondents were found to be having more internal LOC as against singles, thereby supporting H_7 . Additionally, singles were more willing to buy foreign products as compared to married respondents with mean 3.91, sd 1.156 as against mean 3.729, sd 1.085 in that order. This was supported by Pearson Chi-Square value of 22.183, degree of freedom (df) 6 and asymptotic significance .001 ($<.05$), showing a significant difference, hence H_6 is confirmed.

It was established in the study through One Sample T-Test that for overall data, consumers' ethnocentric tendencies differ according to gender, where females were more ethnocentric (mean 4.95, sd 1.219) than males (mean 4.77, sd 1.271). This was further tested and statistically proved through test value $t(237) = 58.787$, $p = .000$. Further analysis also showed that females in both the government and private sectors were more ethnocentric than their male counterparts (mean 4.92, sd .900, mean 4.97, sd 1.332, as against mean 4.84, sd 1.302 and mean 4.70, sd 1.238 correspondingly). Significant differences were also recorded for these two groups of organisations based on gender, with $t(116) = 41.482$, $p = .000$ for government and $t(120) = 41.521$, $p = .000$ for private sector employees, this supports H_5 .

Female employees overall with mean 3.84, sd 1.033 were more willing to buy foreign products as compared to their male counterparts (mean 3.52, sd 1.179) and this difference was significant with $t(237) = 47.679$, $p = .000$. Private sector female employees (mean 3.94, sd 1.014) were most willing to buy foreign products followed by male employees in the same sector (mean 3.68, sd 1.130). The third place was with government sector female employees (mean 3.58, sd 1.084) and the group least willing to buy foreign products was government

male employees with mean 3.39, sd 1.208. The significant differences were further supported with One Sample T-Test [$t(237) = 47.679, p = .000$], which confirms H_6 .

Male employees overall with mean 3.22 and sd .716 were having higher degree of internal LOC than females (mean 3.07 and sd .661), $t(237) = 69.580, p = .000$, it further confirms a significant difference in LOC between these two groups. Further analysis points to the fact that males in private organisations were having highest score for internal LOC (mean 3.39 and sd .668), second was females in government organisations (mean 3.17 and sd .577), third were males in government organisations (mean 3.08 and sd .726) and least level was for females in private organisations (mean 3.03 and sd .695). One Sample T-Test [$t(237) = 69.580, p = .000$] further supports statistically significant difference in LOC levels in these groups as well as H_7 .

8.5.2. Age, Ethnocentrism, WBFP and LOC

Age as a variable was found to have positive correlation with ethnocentrism implying advanced aged people to be more ethnocentric for overall Nigerian respondents ($r = 0.148, n = 238$, the value of $p = <0.022$) and separately for government employees ($r = 0.221, n = 117$, the value of $p = <0.017$). However, no statistically significant relationship was found for private employees. Therefore, it partially supports H_5 for government employees and rejects for private ones. Despite of this finding, older employees overall as well as for government and private ones had negative relationship if it came to WBFP ($r = -0.295, n = 238$, the value of $p = <0.000$; $r = -0.276, n = 117$, the value of $p = <0.003$; $r = -0.224, n = 121$, the value of $p = <0.014$). It means young employees liked buying foreign product as compared to older generation, which backs H_6 . Further for overall and also for government employees, age was negatively correlated with LOC ($r = -0.188, n = 238$, the value of $p = <0.004$; $r = -0.188, n = 117$, the value of $p = <0.043$) implying younger respondents to be having higher degree of internal LOC, which partially supports H_7 . Nevertheless, private employees were found to have no such significant relationship if taken separately, thereby rejecting H_7 here.

8.5.3. Education, Ethnocentrism, WBFP and LOC

The variable education had no statistically significant relationship with ethnocentrism of the overall Nigerian employees (which rejects H_5), except for government employees taken separately who had significant positive correlation ($r = 0.207, n = 117$, the value of $p = <0.025$). Thus if government employees were having higher levels of educational achievements, they were more ethnocentric in nature, which partially supports H_5 . Education also reported a negative correlation with WBFP for overall respondents as well as for bifurcated government and private workers with $r = -0.310, n = 238$, the value of $p = <0.000$, $r = -0.375, n = 117$, the value of $p = <0.000$ and $r = -0.179, n = 121$, the value of $p = <0.049$ in that order. This means on overall basis as well as for government and private employees, more educated they were, less inclination was towards foreign product, so H_6 was supported. Additionally, negative relationship was also discovered vis-à-vis education and LOC with $r = -0.187, n = 238$, the value of $p = <0.004$ and $r = -0.191, n = 117$, the value of $p = <0.039$ for overall and government respondents respectively. It means less the education; more internal LOC was found for the respondents, this partially supports H_7 . Conversely, no statistically significant correlations were found for private employees, in so doing rejecting H_7 .

8.5.4. Work Experience, Ethnocentrism, WBFP and LOC

Work experience of respondents was not statistically correlated to ethnocentrism (which indicates that H_5 was rejected), but negatively related to WBFP for overall respondents with $r = -0.233, n = 238$, the value of $p = <0.000$ and $r = -0.228, n = 117$, the value of $p = <0.014$ for

government employees. It implies that overall and for government employees more work experience they had less was the inclination towards foreign products (in part supporting H₆). Nevertheless, no statistically significant relationship was established for private employees, which implies H₆ was rejected for this category of workers. The increase in work experience for all the respondents taken in total meant they had external LOC ($r = -0.210$, $n = 238$, the value of $p = <0.001$), which was also true for government employees ($r = -0.225$, $n = 117$, the value of $p = <0.015$), to a degree accepting H₇. Private employees showed no such statistically significant correlation, thus rejecting H₇ in this category.

9. Conclusion and Managerial Implications

Principally based in Northern Nigeria where medium level of ethnocentrism found as per the present research establishes that both overall as well as government and private sector employees taken separately are averse to buy foreign made products. However, LOC was not found to be associated with ethnocentrism having no effect on the latter, but government and private sector employees independently as well as combined data pointed that employees having internal LOC were affirmative in their behaviour to acquire imported products. The study further implies to marketing managers to concentrate on products aimed for unmarried consumers (who were found to have external LOC) since they were more enthusiastic to purchase products of foreign origin than their married counterparts as the present study suggests.

Females irrespective of type of organisations overall were found to be more ethnocentric than males, surprisingly however they were also not likely to resist the urge to buy foreign products. Companies operating in Nigeria dealing with overseas products have to bear in mind this finding of the study and keep focusing on luring female clients to sell their products especially for women working in private sector. Additionally, they have to apply more efforts to market their products to male employees in private and more importantly in government sector where there is scope for more marketing efforts, since they are most unlikely to buy foreign products. Important outcome of the study is that females were having more external LOC as compared to males, which point to the fact that in the Nigerian context LOC plays more important part in WBFP as compared to ethnocentrism. Findings further suggest that as compared to older Nigerian employees, which includes government employees, who were more ethnocentric, younger ones, who also happened to have more internal LOC were more positive towards buying imported products. This finding is a positive signal for companies since younger people are likely to live more as compared to old ones thereby increasing the scope of foreign products for a longer time.

One interesting outcome suggests that for overall respondents and government employees, higher educated ones had more external LOC as compared to those who had lesser educational attainments. Another finding of the study suggests that only for government employees higher education meant more ethnocentrism coupled with less preference towards foreign product, for rest of the respondent's educational attainment had no effect on their ethnocentric leanings. Besides, government employees, private ones and also taken as a whole better education steered them to reduced penchant for imported products. This is a clear indication to marketers dealing in foreign products to direct their marketing campaigns towards educated consumers to bring them to their fold since lesser educated ones are already willing to buy foreign items. Experienced employees in terms for work, for whole data as well as government workers had external LOC and were found to be less willing to buy foreign products. Companies dealing in overseas products need to work on less experienced

employees to retain them and focus on experienced ones to bring them to their sway (private employees are statistically not in picture).

10. Limitations and Future Researches

One of the limitations and a guide to impending researches is that Nigeria is diverse and present study is limited to northern areas of the country where it is likely that consumer preferences may change in other parts. Additionally, the research in hand is general in nature vis-à-vis to understand the consumer attitudes, without any product specification, future researches can be on specific products or product categories as well as different consumer groups (as only employees are taken here). To comprehend the customer outlook whether they are generally for or against foreign products or some specific important products they give exception, or for that matter domestically available products they do not buy while other items they buy from foreign countries is another area not covered in the present study and have scope for future researches. The present study only took up Nigeria while there is a great prospect to do cross cultural studies involving more than one country, or for that matter regions or ethnic groups within Nigeria and retaining same variables but at the same time giving more emphasis on LOC, if there are no financial constraints. Studies like that in hand require a more in-depth analysis which is not possible without going for a qualitative research or for that matter longitudinal researches to understand before and after effects of the phenomenon and this is another limitation encountered here and direction for future researches.

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